

INFLUENCE OF VIRAL LIVER DISEASES ON THE STATE OF THE ORAL CAVITY. (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ABSTRACT

Chronic hepatitis today occupy a significant place in the general human pathology, causing significant social and economic damage to society. In the structure of pathological conditions associated with liver damage, the proportion of viral lesions is progressively increasing. Currently, at least 9 types of human hepatitis are known (A, B, C, D, E, G, F, TT, Sen), among which parenteral viral hepatitis deserves special attention, characterized by severe and chronic forms with an outcome in liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma.

In assessing the state of dental health of patients, an important place is occupied by viral lesions of the liver. At the same time, dentists and doctors of other specialties do not pay due attention to the state of the oral cavity in liver diseases [1,2,11,13]. There are very few developments on dental tactics for managing patients with hepatitis. In countries with a high level of dental services, experience has also not been accumulated on this problem. Widespread hepatitis, in particular hepatitis B, requires in-depth dental research.

Key words: dentistry, hepatitis, oral cavity, parodont.

In assessing the condition of dental health patients, viral liver lesions takes important point [1-4] However, dentists and doctors of other specialties do not pay due attention to the condition of the oral cavity in liver diseases [5]

Experience of dental work in infectious departments showed that the effectiveness of diagnosis and treatment of lesions of the oral mucosa depends on the possible early inspection of the patient [6,7]

Dental care in patients even with diagnosed hepatitis is mainly treated due to acute pain. There are few developments on dental tactics for conducting patients with hepatitis. [8, 9]

Parodontic diseases occupy one of the leading places among all dental pathologies, based on the pathogenesis of which are serious violations of microbiocenosis in combination with dysfunction of the immune system.

It is experienced that the pathology of parodonta is often local, but it can have an impact on the disease of internal organs, including the liver and hepatobiliary system [12-19]

The pathogenesis of diseases of the parodonta is based on serious violations of microbiocenosis in combination with dysfunction of the immune system of the organism against the background of generalized inflammatory dystrophic and vascular changes [11].

It is known that the development of pathology of parodonta influences related chronic liver diseases and hepatobiliary system, which currently have a predominantly viral nature [11, 13, 19].

As one of the pathogenetic factors capable of inducing numerous clinical and laboratory phenomena described in chronic viral hepatitis B and C, it can be considered an endotoxin of literate bacteria, causing the development of a complex of pathophysiological, immunological and other biological processes [17, 21, 22]. The main antiendotoxin barrier is the liver [11,17].

With the extension of dysbiotic processes in the oral cavity, as well as other pathological processes in the gastrointestinal tract, the admission of endotoxin into systemic blood flow increases, which can cause an increase in intoxication syndrome and aggravation of chronic inflammation in tissues [17, 22].

The relevance of the complex approach to the pathogenetic treatment of patients with chronic inflammatory diseases of the parodonta, especially in the presence of associated pathology of internal organs and systems [16,19].

The main method of treatment of chronic viral hepatitis is today-interferon therapy. While, the presence of a number of contraindications and side effects limit its application [11, 17]

Parenteral viral hepatitis are one of the global problems not only in medical but also in social terms. First of all, this is due to the significant spread of viral hepatitis, including hepatitis B [21, 27]. According to WHO, in different countries, only viral hepatitis in more than 1mld is infected [21]

An important discovery was the establishment of the possibility of extra-baked virus replication, which does not exclude the probability of skin lesion and mucous

membranes, including oral mucosa (8;9). On the other hand, changes in the oral mucosa, and parodont tissues with acute and chronic infectious liver lesions, in particular with viral hepatitis, attracted the attention of researchers relatively recently. In the scientific literature, we have met only a single work devoted to the state of Parodont tissues and mucosa of the oral cavity with viral hepatitis. At the same time throughout the world, viral hepatitis B (VHB) is considered a professional disease of medical workers dealing with the blood of the sick. Health workers of the VHB are found 2-5 times more often than among the population at all. According to estimated data in the world, annually in the conditions of professional activity of the VHB infected 30 thousand medical workers, while one of them dies daily. [23]

Among medical specialties, the medical professions that are exposed to special risk of infection of VGB: employees of hemodialysis centers, clinical laboratories, Obstetricians - Gynecologists, surgeons, dentists, and among the latest incidence of VGB higher than other medical workers, 1.7 times. In this regard, the interest of intra-hospital VGB in dental practice, as well as patients, and medical staff of this profile are groups of increased "risk" infection of hepatitis virus. According to the American Association of dentists (1981), 14.6% of dentists annually disease VGB. Antibodies to hepatitis virus in dentists are found 4 times more often than among the population in general. [27,28]

Despite the rapid growth of HCV disease in the last 10-15 years, the number of publications on professional infection of dentists and their patients is slightly compared to the VHB. It is probably due to the less variability of hepatitis virus with the external environment and the need for a greater dose of the causative agent for infection of a healthy person, but also mainly artificial (parentative) mechanism of infection, not excluding its relevance in dental practice, especially when co-infection with HBV.

There are many reasons for such dysfunction in dentistry. First of all, this is due to the mass prevalence of dental care, - it needs almost 100% of the population. It should also be noted the specifics of the work of doctors in outpatient dental surgery: constant contact with blood and saliva, the work of the Colum-cutting tools, the aerosol effect when working on modern high-speed equipment, and a significant number of invasive procedures [24,25].

Given the high prevalence of viral hepatitis and that during the year, each person is repeatedly treated for dental care, it is possible to assume that dentists often have contact with infected hepatitis viruses in patients. Moreover, due to the lack of pronounced clinical manifestations of the above-mentioned diseases in the oral cavity, to address dentists, the patient does not need to have an analysis on the possibility of

infection of hepatitis B and C, in the provision of dental care, there is a risk of infection of both medical personnel and patients.

The above indicates the relevance of the issue and the need to improve knowledge on the prevention of infection with viral hepatitis, in particular in the provision of medical dental care.

In chronic hepatitis majority of patients mostly complain about the perversion of taste and feel bitterness in the mouth, especially in the morning, on feelings of burning and tingling in the area of the tongue and lips. The feeling of burning and sickness of the mucous membrane of the mouth is often combined with the feeling of itching, especially expressed in the Sky.

Current hepatitis, especially hepatitis C, is accompanied by the development of out-of-baked manifestations of the disease. Thus, one of the frequent extracellular manifestations of viral hepatitis C is a shegren syndrome, which is the autoimmune defeat of exocrine(primarily salivary and tear) glands. [26-29]

Sialodentitis is revealed in 14-57% of patients with chronic hepatitis. It is important to note that such patients have manifestations, at least one of the two symptoms of the shegren - photocopthalmia or photosystemies.

They develop most often from salivary glands, less often - in lymphatic nodes and bone marrow. Red flat deprivation - another of the extra-baked manifestations of chronic viral hepatitis S. it is proved that red flat lichen is found on average twice more often in patients with hepatitis than in the population. Its manifestations are successfully regressed against the background of anti-virus therapy.

In the cirrhosis of the liver mucous membrane of the oral cavity in the early stages of the disease development is not different from hepatitis described above. In the developed stages of liver cirrhosis against the background of the general symptomatic changes in the coloring of the mucous membrane of the mouth. It becomes pale pink with cyanotic shade, and the veins of the tongue are extended. Secondary deficiency of vitamin a may lead to pronounced hyperkeratosis, especially in areas of physiological orogation of the oral mucosa (solid Sky, gums). In the same areas where mucous membranes traumatized by bite, especially smokers, are noted along with hyperkeratosis of the crack and prolonged non-healing erosion. The mucous membrane of the language atrophies to the level of epithelium desquamation. The gum fires can be single or merged to capture the entire surface of the language. The language becomes smooth hypermated, often the deepening of the natural folds of the language is observed. The skin of red kaima lips and the mucous membrane is interpreted, so can appear mid and lateral cracks of lips, cracks in the corners of the mouth with slow epithelization, prone to infection. The mucous membrane of the mouth is dry, can be

observed phenomena candidacies. In weakened patients, the fungus lesions of the mucosa are chronic. The raid is discharged with difficulty from the plots of the mucous membrane, which can be viewed by likhenopemnye foci as a result of the germination of *Nitya mitselia* [24, 27].

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